

GRAPHENE OXIDE/POLYMER-BASED NANOCOMPOSITE HYDROGEL FOR BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS WITH ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTY

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Heading

Using Graphene Oxide enhanced mechanical properties for poor load-bearing of PVA hydrogel.

- PVA hydrogel has poor load-bearing property. So, PVA hydrogel require enhanced mechanical property for various materials application.

Attaching to a surface and protecting them by encouraging the development of complex interaction

- Preventing biofilm is the key point of antimicrobial effect because of the formation of biofilm is a cause of bacterial infection.

Scheme 1. Preparation of GO-PEI by Epoxy group ring opening

Scheme 2. Preparation of PVA/GO based hydrogel

Figure 1. Used Materials and experimental schematic

- GO was enhanced mechanical property of PVA hydrogel as physical cross-linker.
- PEI can be covalently bonded with GO and give antimicrobial property by high density amine group.
- Zeolites are cages for ion capture and ion-exchanged zeolite give antimicrobial properties to the material by metal ion.

Preparation of Nanoparticle

Figure 2. SEM image of Graphene Oxide nanosheet by Hummer's method

Figure 3. TEM image of EMT Zeolite (a-c), Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) curve (c-e). Particle average size observed 20 nm.

Preparation of GO-PEI

Figure 4. SEM image of GO-PEI (a-f)

Figure 5. FT-IR spectrum of Graphene Oxide (a), GO-PEI (b).

Table 1. Element weight% and Atomic% value of GO-PEI value about Energy Dispersive Spectrometry (EDS)

Element	Weight%	Atomic%
C K	55.37	61.51
N K	10.75	10.24
O K	33.87	28.25
Totals	100.00	

Preparation of GO/Polymer Composite Hydrogel

Figure 6. SEM image of PVA/GO based hydrogel

Figure 7. Tensile stress-strain curves of hydrogels by 2cycles of freeze-thawing. PVA hydrogel (a), PVA/GO based hydrogel (b)

Figure 8. Antimicrobial Test – Decreasing E.Coli colony

Conclusion

- Enhancing mechanical strength of PVA is a key point for various fields of PVA hydrogels because of the poor load-bearing
- In general, It is important to prevent the biofilm which are a major cause of infection for biomedical materials or necessities such as lens, package, clothes and so on.

In this study, we synthesized PVA/GO base hydrogel. GO was used as physical cross-linker of PVA hydrogel and then, improved mechanical property. PEI and ion-exchanged Zeolite was introduced for giving antimicrobial property. Therefore, our research try a novel study for the development of biomedical materials.

Reference

- Qiaomei Luo, Yangyang Shan, Xia Zuo, Anisotropic tough poly(vinyl alcohol)/graphene oxide nanocomposite hydrogels for potential biomedical application, RSC Advances, 2018, 8, 13284
- Zetan Fan, Shu Ping Lau, Polyethyleneimine-Modified Graphene Oxide as a Novel Antibacterial Agent and Its Synergistic Effect with Daptomycin for Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus aureus, ACS Applied Nano Materials, 2018, 1, 1811-1818
- Yan Shi, Dangsheng Xiong, Jianliang Li, Nan Wang, The water-locking and cross-linking effects of graphene oxide on load-bearing capacity of poly(vinyl alcohol) hydrogel, RSC Advance, 2016